

TOOLS4CAP ACADEMY MODULE V

THE ROLE OF INNOVATIVE QUANTITATIVE TOOLS IN DEVELOPING THE CAP'S GREEN ARCHITECTURE AND ECO-SCHEMES

Highlights Report

Introduction

The effective application of modelling tools plays a key role in developing **inclusive and robust CAP Strategic Plans (CSPs) aligned with the New Delivery Model**. This approach shifts from the compliance to performance, rebalancing responsibilities and requiring tailored national interventions based on specific needs. In this context, these tools provide the analytical foundation needed to create adaptable and transparent national strategies that successfully meet overarching EU objectives.

This report builds on the work of the [Tools4CAP Academy – Module V](#), which was designed to offer clear guidance on the use of modelling tools while also analysing their main advantages, limitations, and barriers for their implementation. Furthermore, this module sought to demonstrate their practical application within CAP Strategic Plans through real world scenarios and case studies from the Netherlands and the French region of Occitanie.

ORGANISER:

26 JUNE 2025

ONLINE

39 PARTICIPANTS from 17 COUNTRIES

(Public authorities, governance bodies; researchers; innovators; and other stakeholders relevant to the agricultural sector)

PRESENTATIONS AND RECORDINGS [HERE](#)

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Main highlights from the module

Module V of the [Tools4CAP Academy](#), organised by the European Association for Innovation in Local Development ([AEIDL](#)), was specifically dedicated to present modelling and forecasting tools, linked to **innovative quantitative methods for eco-schemes and green architecture** to analyse the impact of the CAP Strategic Plans. The module was held online on 26 of June 2025, with 39 professionals from 17 countries registered.

This module is the result of the work undertaken by [Wageningen Social & Economic Research](#) (WUR), as detailed in the report [Methodological Guidelines](#), which aims to encourage end users to apply modelling tools during the design and implementation of the CAP Strategic Plans.

Using appropriate modelling tools play a critical role in ensuring the effectiveness and inclusiveness of CAP Strategic Plans and aligning plans with the demands of the New Delivery Model, creating robust, adaptable and transparent CSPs aligned with EU-wide objectives.

Ana González, from Wageningen Social & Economic Research, highlighted that modelling tools offer quantitative insights which can support us to **better understand complex relationships between economic, environmental, and social aspects**, including key trade-offs. This is vital for an integrated approach to policymaking. For an 'informative' application, it is also crucial that models represent the key variables and their interactions within the system under consideration, sometimes requiring the combination of economic insights, agronomic knowledge, etc. If relevant, tools (use in isolation or their combination) should cover all stages of the supply chain and properly reflect market dynamics. To the extent possible, farmer behaviour/decisions and local conditions should be also taken into account.

This module forms part of the [Tools4CAP Academy](#), which aims to provide a framework for capacity building and peer – learning to develop an attractive and tailored training programme to meet the end users' needs. [Tools4CAP](#), coordinated by [ECORYS](#), is a project embedded in Horizon Programme that involves 21 partner organisations from 18 EU countries with outstanding expertise in economic, environmental, climate and social issues, new data sources and monitoring technologies, as well as in stakeholder engagement, social, environmental, and animal welfare-related data and indicators, in agricultural and rural development contexts.

General overview: Modelling tools

Ana González

Wageningen Social & Economic Research

The guidelines presented in the fifth module and outlined in the document were developed within the framework of the task [Screening and development of innovative quantitative tools](#). Some of these tools have been selected to be implemented in the case studies carried out in the [Replication lab: demonstration, support to adaptation and uptake](#).

In the context of Tools4CAP, the label ‘modelling tools’ refers to a **set of mathematical/ econometric models and methodologies for analysis to carry out ex-ante and ex-post evaluations of the CAP**, generating quantitative evidence based on statistical data. These tools play a crucial role, providing a methodology to conduct ex-ante assessment of the potential impact of alternative policy measures, as well as for the mid-term evaluations and ex-post assessments. In a nutshell, **the role of these tools is to provide quantitative insights to help policymakers understand potential impacts, as well as the impacts so far**, thus enabling them to make more informed policy decisions.

The guidelines presented during the module have been prepared by paying special attention to the practical aspects of their use in order to illustrate the potential contribution to the policy-making process. However, the main focus is on sharing key lessons that could help when thinking of conducting a similar type of analysis.

While no single tool can address all policy questions, the proper use of modelling tools can significantly support adaptive management. Modelling tools allows policymakers to anticipate trends, simulate policy impacts, and evaluate various scenarios, thereby improving the coherence, legitimacy, and transparency of the CSPs.

Ana González, Wageningen Social & Economic Research

BROAD CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	TOOLS
Large-scale modelling tools	Quantitative models that primarily focus on simulating scenarios, interventions, or impacts. In the context of Tools4CAP, large scale refers to models which are EU-wide or global, including details at MS level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AGMEMOD • CAPRI • GLOBIOM • MAGNET • MITERRA-Europe
Small-scale modelling tools	Heterogeneous set of tools. It also includes simulation models. In some cases, their geographical scope is more limited than in the previous case, e.g. only a country is covered. These tools also have higher level of granularity, and they can include regions and/or farm types. This category also includes modelling tools which have a simpler structure (e.g. excel-based calculators)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eco-scheme farm simulation tool • Farm income FADN – based calculation tool • FARMDYN • FAPRI Ireland Model • FARMIS (DE) • IMF-CAP • KOBALAMI (NL) • iTFarm tool (SI)
Experimental economics	This one allows us to generate data in a controlled setting to analyse relationships between the intervention of interest and people’s actual behaviour or stated intentions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Laboratory (lab experiments) • Contextualised field experiments • Randomised controlled trial • Discrete choice experiment (DCE)

Overview of selected tools. Tools4CAP 2024. Deliverable 2.3

Which steps needs to be followed when using modelling tools?

- 1 **To get started** – End users define the policy/research question and approach the modelling team with the right expertise.
- 2 **Joint effort** – End users and the research team define the scenario 'storyline' and agree on the assumptions, as well as the output indicators that will be produced.
- 3 **Running the model** – The modelling team gathers the inputs that the model needs, simulate the scenario and generate model outcomes.
- 4 **Validation** – Model outcomes are shared with the stakeholders for validation.
- 5 **Finalisation** – The feedback provided by stakeholders is used to fine-tune the modelling exercise and deliver the final set of outcomes.

To conclude this general overview, it is highlighted that a **success implementation of modelling tools depends not only on technical capacity but also on a strong collaboration between modellers and policymakers**. To achieve this, capacity building, clear communication of assumptions and results, stakeholder validation, and thoughtful dissemination are all critical elements.

Discrete Choice Experiment in the region of Occitanie

Pauline Mace

Oréade-Brèche

During the Module, **Pauline Mace (Oréade-Brèche)** presented this tool and all the elements, components and opportunities it presents. DCE provides a structured, evidence-based method to **understand farmers' preferences and behaviours** in relation to agri-environmental measures, including estimates of willingness to pay or accept for specific policy attributes.

The tool also **enhances transparency, coherence and stakeholder engagement** in the policy cycle stimulating enrolment under various policy scenarios, supporting ex-ante evaluation and design of targeted interventions.

	Alternative 1	Alternative 2	Alternative 0
Attribute 1 - Farming restrictions	Level 1 – Moderate (reduced pesticide use)	Level 3 - Strict (no pesticide use)	I do not find any of the proposals suitable – I am not willing to enter the scheme under these conditions
Attribute 2 - Contract duration	Level 3 - 3 years	Level 1 – 5 years	
Attribute 3 - Amount of payment	Level 2 – 150€ per hectare	Level 3 – 200€ per hectare	
Your choice	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Basic components of DCE

Step by step DCE tool:

- ✓ Step one is to define the evaluation or design objective, identifying the decision context. For this step, desk research, consultations and workshops are the main activities to develop.
- ✓ The second step is to develop attributes and levels, identifying, refining and validating policy-relevant attributes. Main tasks for this stage are related to literature review, interviews and focus groups.
- ✓ The next step is to define its key features and their variations. This should be done hand-in-hand with the Managing Authority and, importantly, by talking to farmers and other relevant stakeholders to make sure it makes sense to them.
- ✓ Experimental design and create statistically efficient combinations of tasks and choose elicitation method (opt-out, forced choice, etc). During this stage, it is important to use design softwares such as [Ngenex](#), [JMP](#).
- ✓ Design, test and refine the full survey instrument to ensure clarity, consistency and respondent understanding. Before the big launch, it is recommended to test the survey with a small group of farmers. This trial run helps tweak the survey if needed and refine the final experimental design.
- ✓ Conduct the actual data collection. At this stage, the survey is sent to farmers. They choose their preferred options from the choices we present. This can happen online (often preferred) or in person with trained interviews.
- ✓ The final step is to estimate part-worth utilities, model preferences and heterogeneity (statistical analysis and conclusions). It will be important to translate model outputs into actionable insights. Econometric software (R or Stata) would help.
- ✓ Finally, reporting, communication and dissemination of findings to decision-makers and stakeholders could conclude this methodology.

Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE) is a quantitative stated preference method, used to capture how individuals value different policy features when making the decision to enrol (or not) in a scheme. This tool supports policy makers in design effective policy interventions and optimises uptake.

Pauline Mace, Oréade-Brèche

Questions, reflections and concerns regarding the French case

During the dedicated question and answer space with attendees, several inquiries were raised that facilitated a deeper exploration of the methodological and practical dimensions of the French case in the Occitanie region and its associated Discrete Choice Experiment.

The most notable questions were those regarding **statistical robustness and the interpretation of results**. One question was raised about the ideal number of interviews needed to ensure data validity and the response indicated that *while at least 100 responses are recommended, the precise number adjusts to the complexity of the design, emphasising the existence of a specific formula for its calculation*. This formula takes into account the number of attributes to estimate, the number of choice tasks per respondent and the number of alternatives per task.

Regarding the **main benefits of using DCE in the design and evaluation of CAP Strategic Plans**, audience

pointed out that better understanding of farmers' real preferences, estimation of willingness to pay/ accept to adjust payments levels or improved targeting and relevance of agri-environmental measures were the main selected ones that DCE could be used in the design and evaluation of CAP Strategic Plans.

The interpretation of utility values also generated interest among participants. It was clarified that, *although the direct estimation of willingness to pay was not an objective in this case, these values are crucial for understanding the relative importance of attributes, even without explicit monetisation*. In fact, the absence of a monetary variable in the design was addressed, explaining that while theoretically possible, methodological and contextual reasons led to its omission in favour of realistic and precise results within the study's scope.

Eco-scheme simulation tool in The Netherlands

Roel Jongeneel

Wageningen Social & Economic Research

Remco Schreuder

RVO (Dutch Paying Agency)

In The Netherlands, the intervention is focused on **the analysis and recalibration of the Dutch eco-scheme, a flexible and point-based reward system**, adapted to the specific characteristic of each farm. The aim of the system is to contribute to the achievement of five environmental objectives through 22 eco-activities. This structure is meant to be **flexible and fair, recognising regional differences** and individual farm structures.

A key part of this work is focused on setting point thresholds for different performance models (bronze-silver-gold) and deciding how to distribute points across the five

objectives in different regions, supported by a modelling framework that combines [FARMDYN](#) (simulating farm-level decision-making and its economic impact), [AGMEMOD](#) (projects market prices) and the [eco-scheme simulator](#) (calculates payments). This model allows for evaluating how changes in the scheme's design affect farmer participation and payment outcomes, but even though the full integration is still in development, their combined use already provides valuable support for the program's planning and adjustment.

One of the key lessons from this piece of work was that co-creation with farmers is highly effective. The combination of on-the-ground pilot testing and scientific modelling added significant value. However, it was noted that using models earlier in the process—before the pilots started—could have improved the design of the system.

Roel Jongeneel, Wageningen Social & Economic Research

On the other hand, it was also mentioned the importance of the **Sustainability Rating System (SRS)**, developed by government and supported by farmers and stakeholders that **evaluates farms based on their sustainability actions** in areas like climate, natural resources,

biodiversity, and landscape. Each objective has its own key performance indicators (KPIs), and farmers earn points by implementing relevant measures and the number of points determines the financial payment they receive per hectare.

Because each farm is different, an average payment rate is used to ensure fairness, though the actual amount may vary depending on the farm's score.

Remco Schreuder, RVO (Dutch Paying Agency)

Questions, reflections and concerns regarding the Dutch case

During the session, attendees posed several insightful questions that allowed for a deeper dive into the methodology and application of our models. For instance, **how the models account for environmental impacts**. It was explained that while eco-schemes are fundamentally designed to reduce environmental and climate impacts,

and the framework includes indicators for measuring these outcomes, initial plans for a full environmental impact assessment were adjusted due to resource limitations. The focus shifted to directly supporting farmers in their transition to more sustainable practices through eco-scheme incentives.

Questions were also raised about the **feasibility of applying these models effectively**, given the often-tight deadlines associated with processes like ex-ante evaluations. It was clarified that it is absolutely possible: *even within limited timeframes, these models can establish a robust foundation for subsequent intervention design, significantly enhancing the quality and reliability of policy development, even if their full potential is not realized in the earliest stages* (Remco Schreuder, Dutch CAP Paying Agency).

The discussion then moved to implementation, with attendees asking **if the same point values for measures were applied across the entire Netherlands** and how implementation on farms was monitored. It was mentioned that, *despite contextual differences between Dutch regions, the point system for each measure was kept consistent nationwide*: farm-level implementation was tracked through diverse monitoring activities, specifically tailored to various farm types.

There was also time to ask attendees for **the impact area or elements they think that this model could be replicated in other countries and regions**, and responses shows that the menu points system for farmer flexibility, active farmer participation and feedback, and the simulation tool for farmers and policy would be the most important ones.

Another key question concerned the timeline for **the ex-ante and mid-term review and its implications for policy adaptation**. It was explained that, for this period, the review began in 2023, with intensive data collection continuing throughout 2024, and measurements are adjusted to reflect the diversity of farm types. This review primarily informs the next Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), but, as an ongoing nature task, this can certainly provide valuable insights for potential programmatic adjustments.

Space for open discussion and reflection among participants

During the session, a space was provided for participation to foster a more interactive exchange of ideas, experiences, and opinions. Using digital applications, the **most significant challenges for adopting these types of tools** in the national context were addressed, along with the **kind of resources and support needed** for their implementation.

It is worth noting that time constraints, policy cycle, limitations in data availability, access and quality or the

failure to consider the complex reality of agrifood systems were the most frequently highlighted challenges. Additionally, audience included as other challenges: *the availability and capacity of modellers, political willingness to use this kind of tools or the readiness of the local authorities to process, evaluate and pay for the funding because most of these initiatives are hampered by bureaucracy drive-off farmers*.

Which of the following do you see as **significant challenge** for the practical application and impact of these quantitative innovative tools?

To effectively tackle the challenges identified and ensure the successful implementation of such tools in other regions, it is crucial to identify the specific resources and support mechanism needed to adapt them to local realities. The audience highlighted several key areas such as:

- **Hands-on training tools**, because people need to learn how to use them effectively. This calls for practice-based training approaches using realistic scenarios;
- **A concrete and multi actor approach**, requiring a collaborative effort involving all relevant stakeholders;
- **Technical skills and capacity building process**, to enhance these competences at the local level;
- **Speedy responses of the local agencies**, ensuring problems do not escalate and users receive timely assistance;
- **Dedicated teams to apply these tools**, for sustained implementation and maximum impact; and, finally,

- **Coherent and interesting, encouraging and a well-structured environment** for the adoption of these tools.

Workcloud summarising the session

Next steps

The Academy training session, concluded with a series of next steps, including that the meeting materials and the report on the main elements discussed will be available on the event page and the YouTube channel.

All presentations and recordings are available at the [event page](#).

Get involved in the project, [here](#).

Or sign up for the newsletter, [here](#).

New training modules of the Academy will be published in the near future, [here](#).

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